

Deliverable 3.1

Functional Specification of game tools & platforms

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document describes the needed technical development of existing IPR to appropriate it to the needs identified especially in WP2 and WP4. It outlines the design, requirements, and capabilities of game-based tools and platforms intended for development and deployment. It provides a detailed overview of the functionalities and technical specifications necessary to support targeted case studies. The document also addresses interoperability, scalability, and accessibility standards, ensuring the tools are versatile and inclusive.
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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous development
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMB	Executive Management Board
EC / EU	European Commission / European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
Live Ops	Live Operations

LTI	Learning Tools Interoperability
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (1= low / 9=high)

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable introduces the two platforms (DiBL & PlanetPlay (PP) (formerly: PM)) that are applied throughout the project reflection sessions and will be adapted to cater to the policy makers’ needs as they are uncovered through an iterative agile process. Acknowledging the agile methodology employed by GREAT, coupled with our reliance on pre-existing platforms, the granularity of specifications outlined in this deliverable is less than what is needed for comprehensive specifications for developing new software from the ground up. This means we do not go into the exact specifications of the technology stack or basic features like user management, architecture, data storage, etc., as these are already provided on both platforms. The two platforms serve two entirely different use cases and, as such, cover a broad spectrum, as seen in Table 1 below, which summarises the platforms.

Table 1: Overview of the two solutions available in the GREAT project.

	DiBL: Dilemma (+survey)	PP Survey Tech (+survey)
Summary	Facilitated synchronous multiplayer dilemma-based game solution.	Quick single-player gamified survey solution.
Players / session	6-50	1
Context of use	F2F classroom, or video conference	Online
Facilitated	Yes	No
Duration	30-120 minutes	1-2 minutes
Flow	Branching	Linear
Complexity	Medium	Low
Scoring	10+ variables	1 variable
Anonymous data	Yes (but can be changed)	Yes
Research style	Quantitative and qualitative	Quantitative
Team play	Yes	No
Best for	In-depth exploration	Scale and speed
Reach	Thousands	Millions
Channels	Owned, (earned) NGO, Policy, school partners	Earned, (paid) Game studios partners

For DiBL, the main focus will be on making the tool more accessible for policymakers through a more visual editor, user-friendly dashboard, and templates to get one started quickly. Furthermore, we will add ten languages to support reflection sessions consisting of international case studies.

The PP technical team will focus on technical development efforts to enhance the functionality of their existing data collection technologies and processes.

PP will explore the interface affordances to allow modifications to surveys and survey structures and thereby decrease existing dependencies on technical expertise and resources. Further technical work will be undertaken to improve data management, governed by the requirements of the project [Data Management Plan](#) (DMP), to facilitate collection, collation, monitoring, regulation, archiving and distribution and address interoperability challenges presented by multiple Data formats. It is envisaged that data formats will be interoperable with existing data dashboards or through an Application Programming Interface (API) to be ingested into various existing data structures.

This flexible approach is anticipated to be most useful to the diverse profiles and use case scenarios of stakeholders in the GREAT project.

2. Brief introduction to this deliverable

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will provide new insights into the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU for the benefit of society. Our research will provide insights into the impact of Citizen Science games on European society by conducting case studies that show how games affect citizen participation in European society. GREAT will provide proposals and guidance to show how games can promote and improve dialogue between citizens and political actors.

They will contribute to democratic education to promote awareness of social challenges and to provide feedback on policy-making from citizens in the EU and partner countries. Up-to-date details of GREAT activities are available on the project website www.greatproject.gg.

This document describes how we will repurpose and extend the two current platforms delivered by PP (Survey tech engine) and Serious Games Interactive (DiBL: Dilemma-based-learning-Games) to serve stakeholders and use cases in GREAT.

We must highlight that we will not develop new products as part of the GREAT project but will work with the existing platforms based on what we have discovered through

the case study reflection sessions described in [D2.1](#) Intervention Design. As such, this technical specification will be less prescriptive than a traditional technical specification as we want to leave room for iterations throughout the project and use an agile development approach, where we prioritise the most critical requirements to serve the connection of policy-makers and citizens around especially climate topics.

We will use the two platforms to support the activity design in WP2. Table 1 shows the differences between the two platforms. Overall, PP will target a more significant number of users, reaching up to 3 million gamers, for quick interactions with those who play alone, and the data is centred and gathered around specific questions. DiBL on the other hand, is meant to be facilitated and played in a group, typically reaching 6-50 people at a time, synchronously gathering more complex data involving dilemmas, branching, and free text.

3. Overall objectives

The objectives of Work Package 3 (WP3) are outlined as follows:

1. **Repurpose existing platforms:**

Tailor the existing platforms to address the needs of policy-makers that will be identified throughout the five reflection sessions of WP4 (see [D4.1 Underpinning Research Framework](#)).

2. **Game Development for Case Studies:**

For each case study in WP2, develop a game using DiBL or activate existing games through the PlanetPlay (PP) platform. At least one game will be available for each of the five reflection sessions.

3. **Data Gathering and Visualization:**

Gather and visualise data from each case study for WP4 and WP5.

The KPI section of the Grant Agreement commits explicitly to: *"Demonstration of at least 12 games, and their use in gathering data which is valuable for policy stakeholders."* While this formulation allows for some interpretation, the subsequent section clarifies this commitment.

The two platforms — DiBL and PP — are leveraged to achieve these objectives, each offering a distinct approach to fostering dialogue between citizens and policy-makers through game-based interactions.

- DiBL primarily focuses on designing, creating, and delivering games for facilitated dialogue and reflection. These games empower policy makers to design comprehensive experiences that can be distributed through various channels. Policymakers are responsible for making these games available through facilitators conducting online or in-person sessions or third-party collaborations, such as schools. DiBL emphasises creating new games, with a target of delivering at least six fully designed games during the project. At least two of these will be made entirely in close collaboration with academic partners during the project and can be made available as open games (see definition in section 4).
- With PP, this focuses on leveraging existing gaming ecosystems through its agile survey format, which is integrated into PP's proprietary survey technology. This approach embeds surveys within existing games, enabling insights gathered around climate-related topics. Here, policy-makers' role is less about controlling the gaming experience and more about utilising established gaming channels to collect data. The goal for PP is to provide at least six examples of how its survey technology can be used within existing games to gather valuable data from players (citizens). While DiBL emphasises the creation of new games, PP focuses on activating existing games to engage players and collect insights. These approaches complement each other by exploring different pathways for fostering dialogue and reflection on climate topics.

In total, we will cover 12 games that demonstrate in different ways how to gather valuable data for policy-makers. These different methodologies will be documented and analysed in the case studies described in WP4. The collected data will be available for open access (as defined in Section 4), subject to compliance with GDPR and any sensitivities identified by project partners. This ensures transparency while safeguarding personal and sensitive information.

4. Technology: Open-Access and Open-Source

The project does not aim to develop any technical solutions but rather to repurpose existing technology and platforms as demanded by the initial call-for-projects. The starting point is two proprietary platforms, DiBL and PP (Previously PlayMob, now PlanetPlay), that will be repurposed and extended to cater to GREAT's focus on policy-makers and citizens' involvement. It is not envisioned that any technical deliverables will be open source because they will not be helpful without the corresponding

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proprietary technology platforms they extensively built upon. However, in the proposal, there is mention of several different open-source elements that are described below:

Open-source tools: We will use open-source tools to expand our proprietary platforms where it is sensible. We will not develop open-source tools ourselves. For example, the R-Project should be used for data analysis to not duplicate previous work (mentioned in Part B, page 9).

Open-source assets: This refers to any images made available as open source, typically in developing a game. This does not include existing IPs from partners. For example, imagery or content available that is their intellectual property (Part B, page 12).

Open-source games: These are done in close collaboration with academic partners, and all the work contributed by academic partners will be available as open games in a package with an open-source license. This implies that all assets, script logic, text and images in the project's games will be available so anyone can use them as they want (Part B, pages 6, 12 and 24). This does not include elements in a game outside the current project, like partner IP, including game technology, but could also be pre-existing rights to visuals.

Open games: It is mentioned that games developed by academic partners based on the platforms DiBL and PlanetPlay will be made available. This implies that the games can freely be played after the project is finished for at least 3 years, assuming the underlying platforms are still active.

Open data analytics: This relates to the method applied where different stakeholders are invited to participate in analysing the data as described in the proposal: "It is 'open' in the sense that the methods used are exposed and explained, but the data itself is confidential and thoroughly anonymised before analysis." (Part B, page 6). It also includes an open-source extension of OpenLAIR.

Open data: This refers to data that is gathered during the GREAT project on climate area and is made publicly available. Portions of the data may be aggregated or individual fields removed to avoid identifying the results of individual games industry partners or the volume of their contribution to the dataset as a whole.

The above will be available on the GitHub repository for ease of use, the Zenodo platform, and/or the GREAT website, depending on the most appropriate output.

Open games

The games designed in GREAT for DiBL will be made available in two ways as shown in table 2:

- Open games and surveys (license): Free to be changed by third parties.
- Open games (playable): Free to be played on the platform for.

4.1 Overview Licensing Platforms

Table 2: Overview of the license to platforms used in GREAT.

	DiBL: Dilemma	PP Survey System
Platform type	Fully proprietary technology	
Open source	Not available	
Open games/survey (licence)	Available: text, images and logic progression Third party can freely make changes to the games and/or implement them in another platform	Available: Text and logic progression as survey instruments: Third party can freely make changes to the survey content and/or implement them in another platform
Open games (playable)	Available at least 3 years after project completion	Available per request
GREAT partners	Freely available to all project partners in the context of the project.	

5. Agile methodology

The Agile approach guides the work in WP3, that is a flexible and iterative methodology that is well-suited for research and development projects and used extensively also for developing games. With an agile approach, we emphasise adaptability, collaboration, and co-creation, breaking the project into smaller, manageable units called "sprints."

In the GANTT chart presented in Table 3, we focus on the overall deliverables, but underneath, we run in sprints of typically 1-3 weeks.

This will look slightly different depending on whether we are focused on one of the below:

- **Platform development:** Here, we may have slightly longer sprints - up to 3 weeks due to the heavier technical development, quality assurance, and deployment of a mature platform.
- **Case studies:** Here, rapid sprints and touch points typically run over 1-2 weeks following the methodology in [D2.1](#) Intervention Design (see the 9-step model).

Figure 1: Steps of a case study sprint.

We adhere to the following key principles during our workflow:

- **Iterative development:** Instead of planning the entire project upfront, Agile development allows for continuous iteration and improvement, where we constantly de-risk the project and incorporate the latest learnings.
- **Stakeholder collaboration & co-creation:** Agile encourages close collaboration between developers and stakeholders, including researchers, policy-makers, and end-users. Regular feedback from these stakeholders helps ensure that the project aligns with the intended goals.
- **Adaptability:** Agile embraces that requirements and priorities may change over time. Teams are encouraged to be flexible and responsive to these changes, adjusting their focus in each sprint as needed.
- **Cross-functional Teams:** Agile promotes the idea of self-organising, cross-functional teams that allows us to leverage the full GREAT consortium's skills and expertise.
- **Continuous delivery:** Agile emphasises delivering functional, tested components at the end of each sprint. This ensures that progress is measurable and allows for the early identification of any issues that may arise. This is critical also to ensure collaboration and co-creation.
- **Regular reflection and improvement:** At the end of each sprint, the team reflects on what went well and what could be improved. This continuous feedback loop helps refine processes and enhances the overall efficiency of the development effort.

6. Terminology: Gamification and game mechanics

Over the years, gamification has been popularised to cover a wide range of phenomena where games are used - often simply the notion of considering any game element outside a traditional game, watering down the concept.

In GREAT, we prefer to differentiate between two definitions:

Gamification: "Gamification is using game design elements in non-game contexts" (Deterding, Dixon, Khaled, & Nacke, 2011). These layers will often be put on top of an existing activity, service or product to increase engagement with such—for example, by introducing a level system into a game. Often, gamification uses extrinsic feedback loops within the gameplay experience. Whether you refer to something as gamification is often context-sensitive, which makes it an unsharp concept for describing features in a system like in this deliverable, where we are laying out the technical contents of the platform PlanetPlay and DiBL.

Game mechanics: Game mechanics can be understood as the "verbs" of a game—the actions, behaviours, and control mechanisms available to the player within the game environment (Hunicke, LeBlanc, and Zubek, 2004). These verbs define how players interact with the system and are what fundamentally distinguish games from other media. For instance, in a television show, the primary "verb" is typically "to watch," and this remains constant, even if we ignore interactive formats. Imagine a sci-fi movie: you could replicate its visuals, narrative, and actors in a game format. However, what makes it a game lies in how players engage with its elements through their own agency. For example, players might navigate by avoiding actors, spotting all green objects within three seconds, or answering questions within a time limit. Each action represents a game mechanic—a verb—while the underlying story, visuals, or characters (the "nouns" of the experience) can remain essentially unchanged. In contrast, altering a sci-fi movie's setting, characters, or story would fundamentally transform the movie itself, but not necessarily the game's mechanics if the verbs stayed the same. Game mechanics, therefore, describe a game's technical and interactive elements. Still, their implementation can vary widely in complexity and flexibility, allowing designers to shape unique player experiences.

When we describe the platforms below it will make sense to differentiate between PlanetPlay and DiBL:

PlanetPlay uses a survey engine designed to tap into any gaming eco/system to survey players on their opinions on societal challenges and thus gains a lot of data that

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can provide insights by leveraging the access gaming studios have to vast players. As such, the PlanetPlay engine does not apply gamification or game mechanics directly but looks for seamless ways to integrate a survey into a game experience and the ecosystem of the gaming industry. This approach can harvest valuable data on climate questions within broad gaming communities.

DiBL supports game mechanics as features in the system that may or may not be used for gamification. As the DiBL platform is quite versatile, we can find game mechanics in different layers. However, in the GREAT project we have so far mainly focused on using the DiBL platform for creating facilitated discussions and reflections:

- Game mechanics (building blocks) can be combined in different emergent ways to create games for a facilitated experience. So, you will find mechanics like points, achievements, branching, teams, etc.
- Game templates (recipes) will show how game mechanics can be used to create different types of games that cater to this specific context of facilitated games and activate discussion, reflection and data gathering.
- Game interface (inspiration): Different examples of game-like interfaces provide participants with the idea that they are involved in a game experience.

7. Technical specification of DiBL: Dilemma-based Learning platform

7.1 Current capabilities and usage in GREAT activities

DiBL is a proprietary platform built by partner SGI to make dilemma-based learning games that enable engaging and inclusive facilitator-driven offline or online collaborative experiences. It consists of core elements, shown below that will be used.

Figure 2: DiBL facilitator screen, mobile phone, and the current creator view.

Game player: The end-user experience consists of a game screen for the facilitator, where the game progression is controlled, shared game content is shown, and the effect of participant decisions. There is also a separate game screen for each participant, where they will receive participant-specific information and make participant choices.

Game creator: Here, users use visual creators to set up their dilemma games. The system offers support for the following functionalities that can be utilised in the design of case activities, as follows:

- Single-player choice
- Multi-player choice
- Free-text
- Rating of free-text
- Teams
- Variables
- Logic & branching
- Text, images and video
- Styling

Game analytics: Data is stored on an individual (anonymised) level, so the users can see how each individual has chosen. This data is only available for users with an analytics role or higher. Data exports can be saved as .csv and .xls files.

Admin system: This handles the state of a DiBL case to make it go online, manage files, and assign users.

Figure 3: Detailed zoom-in on the DiBL creator.

7.2 Extended capabilities to support GREAT activities

Below, we describe what has already been identified during the first activities in GREAT as good capabilities to extend and support GREAT activities. This list may change based on future case reflection sessions if new capabilities surface through the cases and can be incorporated into the DiBL platform.

- **Demo access:** We will make signing up for a DiBL demo account easier with the fewest possible barriers to allow higher adaptation across the EU. *TRL level: 2 > 9*
- **Free Tier:** We will make a tier of DiBL, so there is a free access solution after the project finishes. This will allow everyone access to the use cases developed during the GREAT project. *TRL level: 2 > 9*
- **Templates:** To make it faster and easier to get started, we will implement template functionality with the best examples identified throughout the GREAT project. This will aim to include at least five templates: a story-driven game, a

branching simulation game, a collaborative game, and a role-playing game.
TRL level: 3 > 9

- **End-user access to data:** To make the DiBL data more accessible for end-users, it will become available in a simple PDF format.
TRL level: 2 > 9
- **Implement data privacy consent:** The consent will be updated to reflect data use in research projects.
TRL level: 8 > 9
- **API access:** We will provide API access to the data to better integrate stakeholders' dashboards and collaborative data exploration workshops. This will allow us to use multiple existing and known dashboard solutions. We will create an API endpoint for Tinybird or similar to expose DiBL data easily.
TRL level: 4 > 9
- **Script engine:** To allow for more flexible game formats, the script engine has been expanded from v1.0 to a v2.0. *TRL level: 6 > 9*
- **Visual creator:** Currently, the early case reflection sessions have shown that a key barrier is to make the creation more straightforward and more intuitive. We will, therefore, revise the UI and create a more visual experience.
TRL level: 2 > 8

Figure 4: First interactive mock-up of the visual creator in DiBL.

- **Accessibility:** We will optimise font size and readability across the DiBL solution to allow, especially visually impaired, better accessibility. *TRL level: 2 > 9*
- **Localisation:** Currently, DiBL is available in English, German, Danish, and Greek. We will continue to support these also for additional GREAT functionality. We will also make the localisation effort easier by better supporting special character sets across languages. We will also add languages to support reflection sessions and adaptation across the EU: Spanish, Portuguese, French, Dutch, Italian, Norwegian, Finnish, Swedish, Polish and Czech. *TRL level: 7 > 9*
- **Internal Dashboard:** To make data more accessible for stakeholders, we will implement a simple visual dashboard to support stakeholders who require a quick overview of the data visualisation and meaning.

Figure 5: Screenshot of DiBL prototype Dashboard milestone.

7.3 Game examples from DiBL

DiBL is a tool that allows you to create many different formats, spanning a simple survey over a quiz to a simple simulation game. There are numerous ways to make games by using a variety of game mechanics across formats like virtual quizzes, dilemmas, roleplays and escape rooms.

7.3.1 Quiz game

Some may lean more towards an individual quiz that is a simple, most correct answer, whereas others may be more akin to a Kahoot (a real-time quiz system typically used in a classroom setting face-to-face or online).

Below are numerous examples of quiz formats easily made within DiBL: In the below scenarios, the facilitator shares the question, and participants have 30 seconds to answer:

1. **Classic:** The player's answers are correct or wrong. Players see their score to know how well they did. More or less information can be included anywhere depending on preference, e.g., in text, image, video, or web link.
2. **Classic+:** Players get 2 points for the correct answer, 0 for a bad answer, and -1 for hopeless answers. Sometimes, there are multipliers for extra tough questions to double a score.
3. **Classic-Life:** Players get points for right answers, but sometimes there are bombs with answers that lose 1 out of 3 lives.
4. **Classic tips:** Players have access to a limited amount of tips/lifelines that they can activate when they face a particularly challenging question.
5. **Classic-wager:** Players see the question first and can wager up to 3 coins based on how certain they are to get it correct.
6. **Trophy:** A slight variant to all of the above. Players are informed they can earn a trophy (bronze, silver or gold - or whatever other category you want to use), and at the end, they are rewarded the trophy according to the number of answers they answered correctly or their total score.
7. **Teams:** For all of the above variants, players work together in teams with shared lives, tips and scores. Competition can be encouraged throughout by showing how different teams are doing.
8. **Co-op:** Quizzes can be a shared class activity. For example, distributing information among participants requires them to work together to find the answers. You can also take a softer approach where you still play together but share life, so the game ends when three players across the game have lost a life. Or add a small most-valuable-player at the end to show how well they did, but don't necessarily share it in plenary.

In the above, we use game mechanics like scoring, progression, competition, lives, teams, collaboration, teams and lives, achievements.

7.3.2 Dilemma game

Through DiBL's features, various classic, simple games can be made. Examples include branching games, narrative-driven scenarios, interactive stories, and dilemma games. These can be focused more on a facilitated plenary experience, team-based, or individual. You can even shift between the different modes. Here, we will not include the purely individual as it is not a use case; we typically find in facilitated plenary settings that is DiBL's focus.

1. **Scenario-driven game:** Here, the main driver is the narrative, where you are challenged to consider different choices at key points. Each participant votes,

and this is shown live. In a facilitated scenario, the engagement driver is typically to see what other participants answered and to provide the facilitator with a backdrop to make more interesting explorations into a topic.

2. **Branching scenario:** This has a similar dynamic to live voting, but now the game can branch depending on the majority choice of players. For this variant, the facilitator can differentiate between at least nine different models for creating such scenarios as described by Marie-Laure Ryan (1991). There can be different branches and ends depending on the player’s choices.
3. **Branching simulation:** In this variant, players can collect actions and votes across the simulations and not just have a branch depending on the latest choice. Instead, players can have a rolling variable like *being proactive*, and if they continue to make choices towards that variable, something else will happen compared to choosing *reactive* options. Player choice early on can impact later branches, e.g., whether you brought water or not, and you may need more water halfway through the game.
4. **Mixed individual/teams:** Facilitators can take any of the above approaches but make minor detours depending on individual choices. For example, halfway through the game, participants will have to deal with a series of choices on their own before merging back into the main flow. This can also be done in teams. Team 1 goes down the left path, where they need to solve maths questions, and Team 2 travels the right path to solve a logic puzzle.

Figure 6: Screenshot of a designed free-text brainstorm in the Waterwise case.

7.3.3 Virtual roleplay

As described in the above example, you can shift between modes where either individual, team and/or majority choices drive the game experience. It is worth exploring some interesting dynamics related to this shift. Fundamentally, it activates several roleplay mechanics like imperfect information, distributed information, different agendas, etc.

1. **Different perspectives:** Typically, the starting points for a lot of virtual roleplay. You take on different roles either in teams or individually. This will inform your discussion and reflection as the game scenario evolves.
2. **Opposing agendas:** A more competitive variant of the different perspective's version, where you now have opposing agendas and different win conditions. For example, different political groups or stakeholders trying to advance their position to either introduce a Co2 tax on heavy industries or have reasons to hinder a Co2 tax. One group strongly supports this, and another opposes it, while other players are neutral. As the game advances, you will change position across questions, so in one question, you may need to gather support for your position to gather points, whereas in another, you decide what group gets points. So, in the game design, you must carefully ensure a good balance as the game evolves.
3. **Jig-saw:** Here, teams have to collaborate while solving different parts of the challenge and/or having access to different pieces of the puzzles. Unless they collaborate, they cannot progress.
4. **Traitors:** This is a classic mechanism that can be used in any complex dilemma game. Here, one or more participants are told they should sabotage their team or a specific topic without getting caught.
5. **Shifting sands:** Through public or hidden events, a team's goal or allegiance is shifting as the game evolves.

Figure 7: A case introduction and the teams you can play as.

Figure 8: Choose a mission and on the current city stats.

Figure 9: An introduction to the city you are helping.

The Johnson family

The Johnson family gathers around the dinner table, they have heard the news, water shortages are becoming a reality, and every home needs to find one way to waste less water.

Dad, with a furrowed brow says “I think we could be more efficient with our laundry. SOME people in this house seem to have too many clothes to wash”

Mum and daughter give Dad a sharp look. The daughter says “Well, have you noticed how we wash dishes, the tap is running through the day”

Mum chimes in “We spend too long in the bathroom getting ready, I am sure we could all save a little water there.”

Figure 10: A case study on water management.

Figure 11: Visualisation of the flow creator used for creating Waterwise.

7.3.4 Virtual Escape Rooms

A format that has gained more attention in recent years is the opportunity to create virtual escape rooms in a physical room (like a classroom) to create a clear purpose, a narrative frame for progression, and increased engagement. While DiBL has yet to be used for this, it should have most of the necessary features to support it.

Ultimately, a virtual escape room involves a narrative progression with checkpoints (puzzles) where you must input the right results. Depending on your input, different events (branches) can happen. In DiBL, you can create a page with an image of a puzzle the players must figure out. Either they can each input their answer, or the facilitator can make the ultimate choice - or a different variant of this.

In the above, we use variations of mechanics and bake them into game templates, where we use the game affordances to encourage the behaviour we want that generally goes away from quick answers towards reflection. For example, we do not support a hard timer that automatically pushes people further in the game but leaves this to the facilitator to control. Nor do we square points with the speed of a player's response as it is counter-productive to most reflection learning and discussion - while also lowering data quality from pushing the wrong buttons in a hectic situation.

8. Technical specification of PP: An insights survey platform

8.1 Current capabilities and usage in GREAT activities

The PP Platform will be deployed to engage gamers internationally throughout the project on the topic of the climate crisis, where it has already been used extensively. The platform leverages existing 'hit' mobile games as the channel for a two-way conversation with the global audience, reaching all corners of the planet anonymously and privately, including reaching minority and underrepresented groups.

The platform has three key components that are utilised and expanded based on the reflection sessions in the current project, so the current platform can be repurposed to support these requirements and learnings. The platform can be modified after each case study as we deploy and learn and may have variations depending on the scenario and stakeholders.

Figure 12: Visualisation of the life cycle of PlanetPlay (formerly PlayMob).

8.2 Overview of the PlanetPlay Platform

The three key areas of the PP platform are:

Survey Tech is a customisable survey system that can be deployed and managed at scale with multi-language support and data segmentation by granular distribution channels.

This engagement tool will be deployed to engage, gather anonymous insights, and learn more about the player. Using a custom survey engine and drawing on pre-existing datasets, themes such as transport, energy, farms and food, nature, protecting people and the green economy will be tackled. The survey format also appeals to a broad range of gamers, and the popularity and familiarity of the selected engagement format will secure high participation. Question design and development will be supported by a team of experts, including researchers well-versed in behavioural psychology.

Distribution - via in-game links or in-game advertising space. The main channel to reach a diverse and representative audience will be through existing hit mobile games such as Candy Crush, Subway Surfers and many more. The power of this approach is shown by the distribution by PlanetPlay of 'Mission 1.5' to 33 million people across 50 countries in 22 languages (<https://www.undp.org/publications/peoples-climate-vote>).

Data Management - collect and manage data from various distribution channels and present it in a GREAT Project internal dashboard. This live-ops overview gives access to a basic, initial summary of data collected and how to obtain it for in-depth analysis. Data collected includes:

- answers given to a set of questions
- which host game the player came from
- which platform (if not a game) the player comes from, such as a specific website or social media channel, and
- whether the player clicked to learn/do more.

Figure 13: Visualisation of the Play2Act survey inserted inside a game.

Figure 14: Visualisation of the Play2Act survey inserted inside a game.

Actions and data are tracked in the PP Platform in real-time, enabling optimisation and rapid course correction, if required. The methodology applies equally to broad and highly focused audiences and can be deployed with either the rigour of a national poll or by gathering realistic sample sizes based on required confidence levels. PlanetPlay’s existing extensive dataset on climate attitudes in the UK, across 48 demographic buckets, can be used as a reference throughout the project.

8.3 Extended capabilities to support GREAT project activities

Below, we describe what has already been identified during the first activities in the project as good capabilities to extend and support project activities. This list may change based on future case study reflection sessions, if new capabilities surface through the use cases and can be incorporated into the PP platform:

- **Question Branching/Dynamic Questions:** Based on a player's response, a new question will appear, making the survey experience a more personalised one and enabling the platform to gather more implicit and explicit data.
TRL level: 2 > 6 (current > project target)
- **Open Text Fields/Open Forum/AMA:** Within the survey flow (without obstructing the flow), the ability to add in an open text field question to enable players to answer a question freely.
TRL level: 2 > 6
- **Survey Setup Workflow/CMS:** Improved tools to speed up setting up new surveys and feeding in question content, including the ability to manage reusable sets of questions. Making this process more accessible to other GREAT Project partners via an improved user interface also allows for easier experimentation with ChatGPT generated content e.g. a partner generating

content via AI outside of a survey system CMS and then pasting it into the CMS.

TRL level: 3 > 7

- **One-Time-Use:** A key requirement for policy data is not double counting votes, therefore to build in the ability to ensure one-time responses will be important for the validity of this model and the exploitation plan.

TRL level: 4 > 6

- **In-Game Permanent 'Green Button':** A button shown in-game when a new survey is live, which would enable a regular roll out and a familiar format for players. *TRL level: 1 > 6*

- **SDK/Plug-in (Potentially with Unity):** Which would enable games studios to review questions before going live and deciding if they can distribute them or not, and the cadence of when they can share surveys.

TRL level: 1 > 6

- **API:** To feed data from PP platform to stakeholder's data lake or own dashboard, for example, games studios, policy makers etc.

TRL level: 5 > 7

9. GREAT Analytics Dashboard for stakeholders' involvement and analysis

A method that allows policy-makers to visualise the data collected by DiBL and the PP Survey Tech systems in friendly formats and reports is required. Additionally, an intermediary tool for monitoring real-time incoming data to increase citizens' and stakeholders' engagement is needed to guide any necessary changes, which may arise.

To support us with constructing an analytics dashboard for the project, we collaborated with partner DIPF, which provided us with an overview and analysis of available analytics dashboards (e.g. Tremor and shading/ui) from the field of Learning Analytics in two workshops (see section 10). With this information in mind, we aim to implement the best candidate and use that in the GREAT project directly to analyse research results and create inspiration for how to use the existing dashboard for this use case.

To guide us with the implementation of the dashboard, we conducted three workshops around the dashboard (26.11.2023, 19.12.2023, 12.01.2024) to gather data from all consortium members, where the focus was on personas towards the dashboard, the use cases it could serve, and finally, the data input sources. It was concluded that building new and complex bespoke dashboards was unnecessary. However, a new live ops dashboard was identified as valuable. With a live-ops dashboard, we can quickly survey the ongoing activities so that we can easily keep track of progress and early

trends and indicate findings. As GREAT is not a development project (see later in this section on Retool and Tinybird), we will repurpose existing tools to this effect.

Figure 15: Miro board from the workshops held.

An initial analysis of dashboard options can be found below:

- **Build from scratch:** This solution would require more effort than the current project’s overall purpose warrants as we need fairly standard data visualisation.
 Examples: <https://www.tremor.so/> and <https://apexcharts.com/>
- **Build extension for R project:** This ties closely into a specific tool that is already used extensively in consortium but may not be that accessible for newcomers. It also ties us into a specific statistical tool as a middle step rather than having direct access to data.
 Example: <https://shiny.posit.co/>
- **Build with an existing data visualisation platform with some code:** This allows us to integrate data sources as we see fit, and with great flexibility.
 Example : <https://observablehq.com/why-observable>, <http://retool.com>

- **Other existing data visualisation platforms:** Several other solutions offer enough ways to visualise data, but fall short on other requirements to scale access or customise for more bespoke requirements. Example: <https://dashboardbuilder.net/>, <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/> or <https://public.tableau.com/>

We have now prototyped a live ops dashboard based on a combination of Retool and Tinybird that only draws data from the PP Survey Tech platform. Tinybird handles the data sources, and Retool draws the visualisation. However, the plan is also to integrate data from DiBL if the future study is confirmed and the study coordinator specifies the requirements of users for the dashboard.

Tinybird is a highly scalable, third-party data platform powered by a Clickhouse database. It can handle data ingestion via its Events API and optimises how data is aggregated and made available for quick access on a real-time dashboard.

Retool is a low-code dashboard product with many visualisation and interaction components and the ability to add custom logic via JavaScript snippets throughout the dashboard and data integration flow.

Both products are 'hosted' and thus do not require the GREAT Project to manage and maintain any infrastructure of our own. Both also allow for their configurations to be exported, which is helpful for any open-source release requirements specified in the grant agreement.

Currently, the intention is to use Retool as an internal live ops dashboard that policy-makers do not necessarily use directly. Once it is better understood what report formats these policy-makers require, several directions are possible:

1. The Retool live ops dashboard may output straightforward report PDFs directly, consisting of high-level answer summaries.
2. Complete session data could be exported manually by other GREAT project partners via Retool and imported into their preferred data analysis tool to produce a more custom analysis based on their particular data science expertise.
3. The functionality of the Retool dashboard is upgraded to allow for some level of interactive analysis (e.g. answers by particular segmentations).

The project's direction will first require a better understanding of whether our targeted policy-makers would use an interactive tool to manipulate data or if they only required a static report. Once the data collection takes place and the stakeholder consultations are further along in the reflection session 2 case studies relating to the collected data

and their visualisation, we expect that the stakeholder requirement will become much clearer, which will help us to inform more specific requirements of the dashboard.

At this stage, it remains unclear if it is efficiently feasible to produce in-depth, policy-maker-targeted data analysis within this dashboard or if this is better done by other GREAT project partners via third-party tools or even per policy-maker, bespoke reports.

Examples of essential Survey Tech results visualisation on the dashboard:

- session/response volume over time per survey and distribution method
- KPIs like engagement and completion rates
- answers counts per question, visualised as basic bar charts
- geographic origins (country/city) of the survey respondents
- filtered by date ranges
- compare responses to the same question set to other distributions
- download links to aggregate summaries and raw response data
- simple PDF download links so save charts and data visible on the screen

Examples of more in-depth analysis done in bespoke reports outside of the dashboard:

- response trends (people who replied to one question one way also answered similarly to other questions)
- mixing survey responses with third-party data (including Learning Activities)
- AI-driven data analysis
- geo data-based analysis
- more complicated or visually appealing chart types
- free-form text response analysis (sentiment analysis)
- policy maker interactive access to the responses (they segment/compare as desired)

We will create a data pipeline that takes Survey Tech and DiBL results from their respective live databases and processes data into a format suitable for archival and dissemination to partners performing in-depth data analysis. This will ensure that the dashboard has the most up-to-date data in one place and reduce the manual steps around the export workflow.

Figure 16: Screenshot of the prototype of the live ops dashboard.

Figure 17: Screenshot of the prototype of the live ops dashboard.

10. Insights from DIPF Learning Analytics research for game analytics

10.1 Overview of DIPF activities for GREAT analytics

This deliverable also builds on the research insights gained by the partner DIPF on their Learning Analytics (LA) research. In light of the recent critical discourse within the LA field, specifically the evaluations by Weidlich, Gasevic, and Drachslar (2022), as well as Hicks *et al.* (2022), the LA research program has committed to measure the reliability and validity of achieved learning goals and outcomes of participants in educational scenarios. The program mainly focuses on defining the causal impact of LA on educational outcomes, aiming to close the gap of having poor data collection to measure the learning outcomes of learners as identified in previous research practices. The GREAT project leverages these advancements in the LA field, transferring key methodologies to ensure the collection and analysis of high-quality, relevant data from the gaming platforms DiBL and PP. This approach generates reliable insights to inform evidence-based policymaking, reinforcing the project's commitment to rigorous and impactful research practices. The forward-thinking approach of LA is exemplified by the foundational work of Ahmad *et al.* (2022) and the consequent establishment of the Learning Analytics Indicator Repository (OpenLAIR¹).

¹ <https://edutec.science/products/>

Figure 18: OpenLAIR view on papers referring to the indicator 'engagement'.

OpenLAIR (<https://edutec-openlair.github.io/>) is a learning analytics tool that helps course designers, teachers, students and educational researchers to select the most appropriate LA indicators for certain learning activities to gain reliable insights into the performance of the students during their learning. DIPF has extended it to incorporate research insights for LA indicators for games and gaming platforms (see Figure 19). OpenLAIR fosters the creation of 'Data-enriched Learning Activities' (DeLA), which stand in contrast to the traditional log-file data from a database of information or learning management systems, often offering a fragmented view of the learning journey. DeLAs are precisely tailored to correspond with actual learning tasks, producing data that is not only aligned but also highly indicative of both the learning process and outcomes. This precision ensures that the analytics represent the most accurate digital learning reflection of the knowledge gained by participants in DeLA. The adaptability of DeLAs is evidenced by their application across various learning scenarios, as showcased in DIPF's work on reading comprehension (Biedermann *et al.*, 2023), written text analysis (Gombert *et al.*, 2022; 2024), collaborative learning facilitation (Menzel *et al.*, 2023), and concept modelling (Drachsler *et al.*, 2023). A critical element of the DeLAs is a tailored feedback delivery system (Ciordas-Hertel, Schneider & Drachsler, 2020), which manifests through comprehensive information dashboards. These dashboards display data and facilitate the interpretation and actionable usage of the outcomes, supporting educators and learners in monitoring and improving the educational process. Within the GREAT project, we adapt and integrate insights from the OpenLAIR indicator repository, the design principles of

DeLAs, and the visualization techniques used in Learning Analytics dashboards into both gaming platforms, DiBL and PP.

10.2 Extension of DIPF analytics research to GREAT game platforms

The LA research initiative's advancements and the development of DeLAs contributed to the adoption of the DiBL platform to the GREAT project objectives. By leveraging the adaptive nature of DeLAs, we can extend their application to the design of educational games (see Figure 20). These approaches can be transferred to the game mechanics of the gaming platform in the GREAT project. We, therefore, will look at a DiBL game as an educational program where learners are expected to learn about certain learning goals and gain specific learning outcomes. The alignment of game mechanics with learning tasks allows for collecting data intrinsically linked to dedicated learning goals and outcomes, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of the learning process in a dynamic and interactive environment. By carefully designing DeLAs within gaming scenarios, we can ensure that every aspect of gameplay is purposeful and contributes to the learning objectives.

The visual representation of data through dashboards is a critical component in interpreting the success of learning interventions. The feedback system developed within the DIPF LA research can be considered for creating dashboards for the DiBL platform and the PP gaming environments. These dashboards will display outcomes and provide actionable insights into the effectiveness of game-based learning activities. By tracking key performance indicators derived from DeLA data, educators, learners, policy-makers, and managers can monitor progress and identify key action areas. The dashboards can be customised to reflect the unique analytics of each game, enabling a tailored approach to learning analytics to gain insights into the competencies that the players should gain.

10.3 Knowledge transfer workshops

As outlined in this section, two knowledge transfer workshops facilitated by DIPF have already been conducted to establish a foundation for log-data collection on overarching constructs, such as policy making. The first workshop occurred during the Copenhagen Consortium Meeting, while the second was organized as an online session. As the development of the gaming platforms progresses, we are considering a third workshop focused on leveraging the role of generative AI to analyse the data collected from the case studies.

Workshop 1: Integrating LA Research into Game-Based Learning

Focus:

Understanding the intersection of LA research, DeLAs, and educational game design.

Content:

- Overview of LA research findings relevant to game-based learning.
- Case studies on successful integration of DeLAs in educational games.

Workshop 2: Tailoring Learning Activities Using DeLAs Concept

Focus: Designing targeted learning activities within games to measure desired learning outcomes.

Content:

- Strategies for mapping game activities to learning objectives.
- Techniques for data enrichment within game design to enhance learning analytics.

Workshop 3: Data Visualization and Dashboard Customization (Pending)

Focus:

Developing custom dashboards to visualize learning progress and outcomes from educational games.

Content:

- Interactive sessions on dashboard development tools and software.
- Guided practice in customizing dashboards to meet project-specific needs.

These transfer workshops will ensure that the GREAT project not only harnesses the potential of LA research and DeLAs but also effectively applies these insights to enhance digital learning through game-based platforms such as DiBL and PP. The emphasis on data-driven decision-making will ensure that the project's learning interventions are both practical and measurable.

11. Tasks and Deliverables

Based on the time plan defined in the grant agreement, we have specified below the work in WP3. The GANTT chart is structured in 3 areas:

- **MVP Analytics tools module:** PP leads the work focusing on providing a live-ops dashboard currently in a prototype stage. SGI will expand on it and provide API access. This solution will be used in the first reflection sessions, and a

workshop will be conducted to make adjustments to include data streams. Visualisations drawing especially on the research insights from DIPF through a workshop format. To ensure continuous and maximum knowledge transfer brought closest to market, we plan three workshops: Workshop 1 focuses on LA research in GBL and happens just after the initial pilots that can form a basis for the initial workshop. This work continues before reflection session three starts, where the step 9 model is validated and established with reflection session 2. Finally, a third workshop will be conducted when data has been gathered for the first half of the reflection session 3 case studies, so there is accurate data to work with.

- **MVP Technical platform:** This task aims to provide the existing platforms and support the different case study stakeholders in obtaining the most out of the platform while feeding back requirements to enhance the platform. The goal is that the project, after the first three reflection sessions, will have an MVP technical platform that can be used for reflection sessions #4 and #5, which can then result in the final adaptation of the platforms based on best practices. The technical platform will be based on the agile approach laid out earlier, which continuously prioritises the most critical features from the backlog per discussion with case study partners.
- **Technical platform:** The technical platform is operational and services the reflection sessions. Systems for sharing data and cases beyond the GREAT project are developed. Based on the best practice features in reflection sessions 1, 2 and 3 (documented in [D2.1](#), D2.2 and D2.3 containing the Year 1, 2, and 3 Intervention Designs, respectively), are developed in DiBL for especially a visual creator and templates that allow future policy-makers to quickly reap the benefits of the GREAT insights tangibly. PP platform will pinpoint potential features based on workshops and case studies input.

Table 3: GANTT chart of WP3.

12. Inclusion

The DiBL platform is open to all schools, and by using a facilitator, it is possible to adapt to the audience's needs. The facilitator can unpack difficult areas and read aloud text, ensuring at least WCA 2.0 A. More importantly, the platform increases the inclusion of more voices by offering a safe space in a facilitated setting to voice your opinions by anonymously contributing through a mobile device, either through voting or free-text fields. The DiBL platform uses standard HTML, which supports the most commonly used extensions for accessibility. This would also include built-in text-to-speech on mobile devices or dedicated plug-ins. The PP Survey tech is restricted by how it is embedded in the gaming eco-system but has partnered with a diverse group of game studios cutting across diverse genres, providing a broad group of players, and not just one niche group. Furthermore, it has focused on ensuring a broad geographical representation through meta-tagging of participants' player participation.

13. Quality Assurance Procedures

In the DiBL games, we use the X-Ray test suite in JIRA to manage automated testing, thus reducing the need for manual testing and providing a smooth CI/CD process. We use Playwright to run the test on the front end.

PP uses TypeScript to catch some problems right within the development IDE. Code changes are reviewed via git pull requests by the technical lead and then tested by several other team members on a test environment before they are integrated into the production branch. A CI/CD step ensures that a new release builds properly before deployment to production. Additionally, survey-specific configuration data is validated to ensure that there are no inconsistencies (e.g. questions with no answers).

The [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook deliverable contains details of compliance and standards such as advertising, etc.

14. Roles, Responsibilities and Collaboration

PP Survey Tech: PP & PlanetPlay

- Jude Ower, CEO, PP
- Joost Schuur, Technical Integration manager, Planet Play
- Sandro Oliveira Technical Lead, PlanetPlay
- Richard Vignais, Head of Product, PlanetPlay

DiBL: Serious Games Interactive

- Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen, CEO Serious Games Interactive
- Martin Lund, CTO DiBL

Analytics & Dashboard

- **PP**: Responsible for this task, which includes setting up Tinybird and Retool. Also provide exports in other formats from PP if requested.
- **SGI**: Responsible for providing API access to integrate DiBL data into the live-ops dashboard. Also provide exports in other formats from DiBL if requested.
- **DiPF**: Provide insights into an existing learning analytics platform, best praxis on data formats, analytics, dashboards, and feedback on use cases for the dashboard.

- **UoB:** Provide insights into best praxis on data formats, analytics, dashboard and feedback on use cases for the dashboard.
- **ZSI:** Provide feedback on use cases for the dashboard especially in relation to evaluation framework and citizenship science.

Case studies

- **ZSI, UNIR, FU and UoB:** Will be responsible for providing case studies to inform the set-up and needs of the DiBL and PP platforms.

Figure 19: DiBL Green Jobs case study co-created with ZSI and Klimafonds.

15. Data Protection and Privacy

15.1 Data Protection

We follow several best practices in this project, e.g. OWASP, as follows:

1. Data collected by the Survey Tech system is never personally identifiable.
2. Least privilege roles approach. Only a tiny technical team has direct access to the database systems that hold the data.
3. Testing and production use separate database environments.

4. Access to production environments (and the ability to generate further access) is only assigned as absolutely needed.
5. Access to third-party tools (e.g. Tinybird) is only available through permission-based, named (not shared) accounts (subject to their strict password policies, etc).
6. When shared via an API with the dashboard e.g., authorisation is required by the API endpoint.
7. Access by outside partners is limited to only their relevant surveys and regulated by named accounts.
8. Public data is only ever made available for very tailored purposes (e.g. when creating a highly specific data panel for a public web page).

15.2 Data Privacy

We follow the principles described in the [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook, relating to collecting consent for participation, but in general, all data is anonymous on the platforms. For evaluation purposes, we may add a key to connect a response in the platform with responses in other survey tools. The data will be pseudonymized, and participants will need to be informed.

15.3 Ethics

We have followed the principles laid out in the [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook in relation to research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

The responsibility for the research ethics using the technology in this deliverable lies with the Academic Lead of each case Study, as stated in deliverable [D4.2 GREAT Case Study Plan](#). This is an area the Academic Partner will guide the technology partners to ensure the highest standards of ethics are adhered to.

16. Open Access, Open Research Data & IPR

We will make as much material and data available as possible. However, the exact nature of this will be part of the [D6.2](#) Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. Note that the technical deliverables will not be made open source as these are the intellectual property of commercial partners - SGI and PP. In the GREAT project, we are

repurposing existing games and will not be producing any open-source games within the parameters of SGI and PP. Except for the last reflection session 5, where the academic partners will develop open games as a proof of concept.

17. Closing remarks

As hinted in the introduction, this technical specification is more open than typical for such formats. This allows for a more agile feedback loop with reflection sessions carried out throughout the project. As described in [D2.1 Intervention Design](#), we see that we have to extend a high degree of flexibility in the method, and we have just scratched the surface.

The above list of requirements (sections 7 and 8) for both the DiBL and PP platforms should be seen as a list of features we have validated in the first pilot case studies but not encompassing all the adaptations we may need to make throughout the project. This depends on the requirements of the policy-maker stakeholders who will be enrolled going forward. We may see more project-specific requirements around game design or visuals, specific interactions needed by one stakeholder like free-text in PP, or extended visualisation.

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